

A Deep Learning-Based Approach For Inappropriate Content Detection And Classification of YouTube Videos

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Abstract— The exponential expansion of YouTube videos has drawn billions of viewers, the vast majority of them are young. Malicious uploaders see this platform as an opportunity to transmit disturbing visual materials, such as using animated cartoon videos to share improper material with youngsters. As a result, it is strongly recommended that social media networks include an automatic real-time video content filtering method. This paper proposes a revolutionary deep learning-based architecture for detecting and classifying improper content in films. To accomplish this, the proposed framework uses an ImageNet pre-trained convolutional neural network (CNN) model called EfficientNet-B7 to extract video descriptors, which are then fed into a bidirectional long short-term memory (BiLSTM) network to learn effective video representations and perform multiclass video classification. Following BiLSTM, an attention mechanism is integrated to apply attention probability distribution to the network. These models are tested on a manually annotated dataset of 111,156 cartoon clips sourced from YouTube. Experimental results show that EfficientNet-BiLSTM (accuracy D 95.66%) outperforms the attention mechanism-based EfficientNet-BiLSTM (accuracy D 95.30%) framework. Second, typical machine learning classifiers perform significantly worse than deep learning classifiers. Overall, the architecture of Efficient Net and BiLSTM with 128 hidden units achieved cutting-edge performance (f1 score D 0.9267).

Keywords: BiLSTM, deep learning, SVM, Machine learning, YouTube.

I. INTRODUCTION

Misuse The number of videos created and consumed on social media platforms has increased dramatically in recent years. YouTube is the most popular social networking site for video sharing, with a large number of videos in a variety of genres. According to YouTube statistics [1], the global user base of YouTube exceeds 2 billion registered users, with more than 500 hours of video content produced per minute. As a result, billions of hours of video are available, allowing users of all ages to discover both general and personalised content [2]. Given such a massive crowd-sourced database, it is incredibly difficult to monitor and regulate uploaded information in accordance with platform requirements. This opens the door for malevolent people to engage in spamming operations by fooling audiences with falsely marketed content (e.g., video, audio, text). The most disruptive behaviour of malicious individuals is to expose young audiences to distressing content, especially when it is posed as safe for them. Children currently spend the majority of their time on the Internet, and the YouTube platform has clearly established itself as a viable alternative to traditional screen media (e.g., television) [3], [4]. The YouTube press release [5] also validated the social media site's great appeal among younger audiences compared to other age groups, with the rationale being less limitations [6]. Unlike television, children can be exposed to any form of content on the Internet due to a lack of controls. Exposing children to unpleasant content is one of several online safety hazards, including cyberbullying, predators, and hate [7]. According to Bushman and Huesmann [8], repeated exposure to upsetting video content can affect children's behaviour, emotions, and cognition in both the short and long term. Many reports [9]_[12] have noticed a pattern of disseminating improper information in children's videos. This trend gained traction when mainstream media reported on the Elsatgate controversy [13], [14], in which such video material was discovered on YouTube featuring famous childhood cartoon characters (i.e., Disney characters, superheroes, etc.) portrayed in disturbing scenes, such as performing mild violence, stealing, drinking alcohol, and engaging in nudity or sexual

activity. In an attempt to create a safe online platform, laws such as the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA) require websites to have safety procedures for children under the age of 13.

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There is an option to filter out dangerous content. Aside from that, YouTube created the YouTube Kids application to provide parental control over videos that have been approved as safe for a specific age group of children [15]. Despite YouTube's efforts to restrict the harmful content phenomenon, upsetting videos continue to surface [16]_[19], including on YouTube Kids [20], due to the difficulty of detecting such content. One possible explanation is that YouTube's high volume of video uploads per minute renders it vulnerable to harmful content. In addition, YouTube's decision-making algorithms rely extensively on video metadata. As a result, changing films based on metadata and community tagging is insufficient to ensure children's safety [21]. There have been numerous instances on YouTube when safe video titles and thumbnails have been utilised to conceal upsetting content in order to deceive children and parents. Another prevalent strategy used by unscrupulous uploaders is the sparse inclusion of kid inappropriate content in videos. Fig. 1 shows an example of such a circumstance in which the movie title and video clips are appropriate for children (as indicated in Fig. 1(a)), yet the video contains objectionable sequences (b) and (c). The disturbing aspect of this example, as well as many other comparable examples, is that these films have millions of views, more likes than dislikes, and have been available for years. Many other situations (as seen in Fig. 1(d)) have been identified in which videos or YouTube channels are not popular yet contain child-safe content, particularly in the form of animated cartoons. The examples show that this problem occurs regardless of channel or videopopularity. Additionally, YouTube has Disabling the dislike function of videos prevented viewers from receiving indirect video content input via statistics.

Because YouTube information is easily changed, it is recommended to use video features for detecting improper content rather than metadata attributes linked with videos [22]. Prior solutions [23]_[28] addressed the difficulty of recognising objectionable content (i.e., violence, pornography, etc.) in films by applying typical hand-crafted characteristics to frame-level data. In recent years, the cutting-edge performance of deep learning has prompted researchers to use it in image and video processing. The most common applications of image/video categorization were convolutional neural networks [29]_[31]. Aside from that, the long-short term memory (LSTM), a subset of the recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture, has proven to be an excellent deep learning model for time-series data processing [32]. As a result, this study focuses on the YouTube multiclass video classification problem by using CNN (EfficientNet-B7) and LSTM to train video effective representations for detecting and classifying inappropriate content. We targeted two sorts of problematic content aimed at young viewers: violence and sexual nudity overtones.

The primary contributions of this work are threefold:

1. We introduce a new CNN (Ef_cientNet-B7) and BiLSTM deep learning framework for Detect and classify unsuitable video content
2. We provide a manually annotated ground truth video collection comprising 1860 minutes (111,561 seconds) of cartoon videos for young children (under 13). All videos are sourced from YouTube using popular cartoon titles as search terms. Each video clip is labelled for either a safe or unsafe class. Videos in the unsafe category are screened for explicit content related to fantasy violence and sexual nudity. We also plan to make this dataset openly available to the scholarly community.
3. We assess the performance of our suggested CNN-BiLSTM framework. Our multiclass video classifier got a validation accuracy of 95.66 percent. Several different cutting-edge machine learning and deep learning architectures are tested and compared for the purpose of detecting improper video content. To summarise, this work can help any video sharing site delete harmful videos or blur/hide any area of a video that contains unsafe information. Second, it may aid in the development of web-based parental control systems such as plugins or browser extensions that automatically filter out inappropriate content for minors. The upcoming sections of the article are listed below: Section II discusses related work in this research area. Section III explains the methodology behind our suggested approach. The experimental setup for the proposed system is provided in Section IV. Section V analyses and discusses the data acquired from the experimental setting. Finally, Section VI ends the work and outlines potential prospective areas for development.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The number of videos created and consumed on social media platforms has increased dramatically in recent years. YouTube is the most popular social networking site for video sharing, with a large number of videos in a variety of genres. According to YouTube statistics [1], the global user base of YouTube exceeds 2 billion registered users, with more than 500 hours of video content produced per minute. As a result, billions of hours of video are available, allowing users of all ages to discover both general and personalised content [2]. Given such a massive crowd-sourced database, it is incredibly difficult to monitor and regulate uploaded information in accordance with platform requirements. This opens the door for malevolent people to engage in spamming operations by fooling audiences with falsely marketed content (e.g., video, audio, text). The most disruptive behaviour of malicious individuals is to expose young audiences to distressing content, especially when it is posed as safe for them. Children currently spend the majority of their time on the Internet, and the YouTube platform has clearly established itself as a viable alternative to traditional screen media (e.g., television) [3], [4]. The YouTube press release [5] also validated the social media site's great appeal among younger audiences compared to other age groups, with the rationale being less limitations [6]. Unlike television, children can be exposed to any form of content on the Internet due to a lack of controls. Exposing children to unpleasant content is one of several online safety hazards, including cyberbullying, predators, and hate [7]. According to Bushman and Huesmann [8], repeated exposure to upsetting video content can affect children's behaviour, emotions, and cognition in both the short and long term. Many reports [9][10] have noticed a pattern of disseminating

improper information in children's videos. This trend gained traction when mainstream media reported on the Elsgate controversy in which such video material was discovered on YouTube featuring famous childhood cartoon characters (i.e., Disney characters, superheroes, etc.) portrayed in disturbing scenes, such as performing mild violence, stealing, drinking alcohol, and engaging in nudity or sexual activity. In an attempt to create a safe online platform, laws such as the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA) require websites to have safety procedures for children under the age of 13.

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There is an option to filter out dangerous content. Aside from that, YouTube created the YouTube Kids application to provide parental control over videos that have been approved as safe for a specific age group of children. Despite YouTube's efforts to restrict the harmful content phenomenon, upsetting videos continue to surface including on YouTube Kids due to the difficulty of detecting such content. One possible explanation is that YouTube's high volume of video uploads per minute renders it vulnerable to harmful content. In addition, YouTube's decision-making algorithms rely extensively on video metadata. As a result, changing films based on metadata and community tagging is insufficient to ensure children's safety. Because YouTube information is easily changed, it is recommended to use video features for detecting improper content rather than metadata attributes linked with videos. Prior solutions addressed the difficulty of recognising objectionable content (i.e., violence, pornography, etc.) in films by applying typical hand-crafted characteristics to frame-level data. In recent years, the cutting-edge performance of deep learning has prompted researchers to use it in image and video processing. The most common applications of image/video categorization were convolutional neural networks. Aside from that, the long-short term memory (LSTM), a subset of the recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture, has proven to be an excellent deep learning model for time-series data processing. As a result, this study focuses on the YouTube multiclass video classification problem by using CNN (EfficientNet-B7) and LSTM to train video effective representations for detecting and classifying inappropriate content. We targeted two sorts of problematic content aimed at young viewers: violence and sexual nudity overtones.

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video that contains unsafe information. Second, it may aid in the development of web-based parental control systems such as plugins or browser extensions that automatically filter out inappropriate content for minors.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system introduces a new CNN (EfficientNet-B7) and BiLSTM-based deep learning architecture to detect and classify improper video content. The system provides a manually annotated ground truth video collection comprising 1860 minutes (111,561 seconds) of cartoon videos for young children (under 13). All videos are sourced from YouTube using popular cartoon titles as search terms. Each video clip is labelled for either a safe or unsafe class. In the risky category, explicit fantasy violence and sexual nudity are monitored in videos. We also plan to make this dataset openly available to the scholarly community.

The system assesses the effectiveness of our suggested CNN-BiLSTM framework. Our multiclass video classifier completed the validation. Accuracy of 95.66%. Several different cutting-edge machine learning and deep learning architectures are tested and compared for the purpose of detecting improper video content, proposed architecture as shown in **FIGURE 1**.

Fig1:Proposed Model Architecture

IV. METHODOLOGY

Defining Objectives and Goals Clearly define the objectives of the project, specifying the desired outcome of the inappropriate content detection and classification. Identify whether the goal is binary (e.g., safe vs. unsafe) or multiclass (e.g., categories of inappropriate content).

Data Acquisition and Preprocessing Curate a comprehensive dataset of YouTube videos representing diverse content, with particular emphasis on videos intended for children. Ensure that the dataset is annotated to denote safe and unsafe content based on specific criteria. Preprocess the video data, including tasks such as frame extraction, normalization, and feature representation, e.g., by using visual representations like frame-level CNN activations or motion vectors, and audio features like spectrograms or MFCCs.

Data Splitting and Augmentation Split the dataset into training, validation, and testing sets to facilitate model evaluation on unseen data. Consider applying data augmentation techniques tailored to video content, such as frame flipping, contrast adjustments, or frame additions, to enhance the diversity and robustness of the training data.

Model Architecture Design Develop a deep learning architecture, possibly a combination of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, or multilayered hybrid models, to effectively capture temporal, spatiotemporal, and audiovisual representations. Experiment with different network architectures, including variations in layer types, sizes, and connectivity, to optimize the model for inappropriate content detection and classification.

Model Compilation and Training Choose appropriate loss functions, optimizers, and evaluation metrics for multiclass video classification, e.g., categorical cross-entropy loss, Adam optimizer, and accuracy metrics. Train the deep learning model on the training dataset while monitoring its performance on the validation set to prevent overfitting.

Evaluation and Validation Evaluate the trained model's performance using the dedicated testing set, assessing metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score to gauge its effectiveness in identifying inappropriate content. Analyze misclassifications to identify patterns or characteristics of misclassified content, aiding in model refinement.

Fine-Tuning and Optimization Fine-tune the model based on insights gathered from the evaluation phase, adjusting hyperparameters, model architectures, or data augmentation strategies to enhance its performance. Experiment with different optimization techniques, such as transfer learning, regularization methods, or ensembling, to further improve the model's robustness and accuracy.

Deployment Preparation Prepare the model for deployment, considering factors like model size, inference speed, and compatibility with deployment platforms. Explore model optimization techniques like quantization, compression, or edge device deployment to ensure efficient and effective real-world usage.

Monitoring and Maintenance Establish a monitoring system to oversee the model's performance in real-world deployment, potentially leveraging techniques like A/B testing or continuous model evaluation. Maintain flexibility for model updates in response to changing content trends, new data availability, or evolving characteristics of inappropriate content in YouTube videos.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Analyzing the results of a deep learning-based approach for detecting and classifying inappropriate content in YouTube videos involves several steps shown in **FIGURE 2 and FIGURE 3**. Here's a structured approach to conducting and presenting this analysis:

[1] 1. Data Collection

- **Dataset:** Description of the dataset used (number of videos, duration, types of content, etc.).
- **Preprocessing:** Steps taken to preprocess the data (e.g., frame extraction, audio processing, text transcription).

Model Architecture

- **Model Description:** Details of the deep learning models used (e.g., CNN, RNN, Transformer models).
- **Training Details:** Training parameters such as learning rate, batch size, epochs, and optimization techniques.
- **Transfer Learning:** If any pre-trained models were used (e.g., ResNet, BERT).

Performance Metrics

- **Accuracy:** Overall accuracy of the model in detecting inappropriate content.
- **Precision, Recall, F1-Score:** Detailed metrics for each class (e.g., violence, hate speech, explicit content).
- **Confusion Matrix:** Visual representation of the performance showing true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives.
- **ROC-AUC:** Receiver Operating Characteristic curve and Area Under Curve for evaluating model performance.

Quantitative Analysis

- **Accuracy:** The overall percentage of correct classifications.
- **Precision:** How many selected items are relevant.
- **Recall:** How many relevant items are selected.
- **F1-Score:** The harmonic mean of precision and recall.

Much better and more accurate results for URL classification are generated by these three crucial qualities

Figure 2: Content Detection

Figure 3: In appropriate content

Figure 4: Safe content

VI. CONCLUSION

In This Paper proposes a revolutionary deep learning-based system for detecting and classifying child inappropriate video content. To extract video features, transfer learning is used in conjunction with the EfficientNet-B7 architecture. The collected video characteristics are fed into the BiLSTM network, where the model learns effective video representations and performs multi-class video classification. All evaluation trials are carried out utilising a manually annotated cartoon video dataset of 111,156 video clips sourced from YouTube. The evaluation results showed that the proposed framework of Efficient Net-BiLSTM (with hidden units D 128) performs better (accuracy 95.66%) than other tested models such as Efficient Net-FC, Efficient Net-SVM, Efficient Net-KNN, Efficient Net-Random Forest, and Efficient NetBiLSTM with attention mechanism-based models (with hidden units D 64, 128, 256, and 512). Furthermore, a performance comparison with existing state-of-the-art models revealed that our BiLSTM-based framework outperformed other existing models and approaches, with the highest recall score of 92.22%. The benefits of the proposed deep learning-based children's unsuitable video content detection system are as follows:

- The system uses EfficientNet-B7 and BiLSTM-based deep learning to filter live-captured movies at 22 fps, taking into account real-time conditions.
- It can help video sharing platforms delete hazardous clips and wipe out uncomfortable frames. It may aid in developing parental control solutions for the internet, such as plugins or browser extensions that automatically filter out harmful content for children.

Furthermore, our methodology for detecting unsuitable children's content on YouTube is independent of YouTube video metadata, which is easily manipulated by fraudulent uploaders to deceive audiences. In the future, we plan to merge the temporal stream of optical low frames with the spatial stream of RGB frames to increase model performance by better comprehending the global representations of video. We also intend to expand the classification labels to target the many forms of improper children content in YouTube videos.

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REFERENCES

- [2] Ceci. YouTube Usage Penetration in the United States 2020, by Age Group. Accessed: Nov 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/296227/us-youtube-reach-age-gender>
- [3] P. Covington, J. Adams, and E. Sargin, "Deep neural networks for YouTube recommendations," in Proc. 10th ACM Conf. Recommender Syst., Sep. 2016, pp. 191-198, doi: 10.1145/2959100.2959190.
- [4] M. M. Neumann and C. Herodotou, "Evaluating YouTube videos for young children," Educ. Inf. Technol., vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 4459-4475, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10639-020-10183-7.
- [5] J. Marsh, L. Law, J. Lahmar, D. Yamada-Rice, B. Parry, and F. Scott, Social Media, Television and Children. Sheffield, U.K.: Univ. Sheffield, 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.stac-study.org/downloads/STAC_Full_Report.pdf
- [6] L. Ceci. YouTube Statistics & Facts. Accessed: Sep. 01, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/topics/2019/youtube/>
- [7] M. M. Neumann and C. Herodotou, "Young children and YouTube: A global phenomenon," Childhood Educ., vol. 96, no. 4, pp. 72-77, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1080/00094056.2020.1796459.
- [8] S. Livingstone, L. Haddon, A. Görzig, and K. Ólafsson, Risks and Safety on the Internet: The Perspective of European Children: Full Findings and Policy Implications From the EU Kids Online Survey of 9-16 Year Olds and Their Parents in 25 Countries. London, U.K.: EU Kids Online, 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/id/eprint/33731>

- [9] B. J. Bushman and L. R. Huesmann, "Short-term and long-term effects of violent media on aggression in children and adults," *Arch.Pediatrics Adolescent Med.*, vol. 160, no. 4, pp. 348_352, 2006, doi: 10.1001/archpedi.160.4.348.
- [10] S. Maheshwari. (2017). On YouTube Kids Startling Videos Slip Past Fil- ters. The New York Times. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/11/04/business/media/youtube-kids-paw-patrol.html>
- [11] C. Hou, X. Wu, and G. Wang, "End-to-end bloody video recognition by audio-visual feature fusion," in *Proc. Chin. Conf. Pattern Recognit. Comput. Vis. (PRCV)*, 2018, pp. 501_510, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-03398-9_43.